

Impact of Health and Safety Practices on Employee Job Performance: Mediating Role of Employee Commitment in Selected Building Construction Companies in Sri Lanka

Bandara S.M.M.S.K.¹, Perera G.D.N.²

¹University of Sri Jayewardenepura, Sri Lanka.

²Professor, Dept. of Human Resource Management, University of Sri Jayewardenepura, Sri Lanka.

Abstract – Health and safety practices bring about umpteen perks to every industry. Building construction industry garners the optimum advantageousness through health and safety practices in order to enhance the employee job performance towards the realizing of its objectives. This study aims to furnish the existing research gap by thoroughly scrutinizing the aforementioned impact in the context of Sri Lankan building construction industry with specifying the skilled labourers. Further, this study broadens the study area by examining the mediating effect of employee commitment to the relationship between health and safety practices and employee job performance. The study was conducted on a sample of 175 skilled labors, and selected by convenient sampling method. Data analysis was carried out with SPSS 23 version analytical software and descriptive, correlation and regression analysis were accompanied. Eventually, the findings reveal that the health and safety practices have a positive and significant impact over employee job performance and employee commitment. Further, it elaborated the positive and significant impact of employee job performance on employee commitment. Moreover, employee commitment contributed positive mediating effect to the relationship of health and safety practices and employee job performance. Hence, the study findings crucially elaborate the rationality of health and safety practices towards the sustainability

development of building construction industry by improving job performance of employees with commitment.

Keywords: Building Construction Industry; Employee Commitment; Employee Job Performance; Health and Safety Practices; Skilled Labourers.

1. INTRODUCTION

Construction industry is classified as one of the most dynamic and responsive sectors in the world [1]. The construction industry and its activities act a flourishing role in the socio-economic development of a county in terms of providing infrastructure, sanitary and employment [2]. Considering the world economy and the construction industry, there are wealth of experiences of construction can be elaborated as the herculean factors for the economic boom [3]. Economic growth through the construction industry mainly relied on the category of country's economic condition such as developed country and developing country.

Building construction is the fundamental categorization among the overall construction industry [4]. Building construction categorized under five sub areas which are residential, farm, industrial building, commercial building and other buildings. It crates employee opportunities, opportunities for new entries and etc towards the socio-economic development of a country [5].

By considering the Sri Lankan context, Sri Lankan government has declared the construction industry as a strategic national asset and it was convinced that the construction industry could be used to garner economic growth and improve the life of living of the Sri Lankans. In the present scenario, Sri Lankan building construction industry is capacious and complex with the technological advancements as well as the man power. On a par with the development of construction industry, drawbacks such as health and safety procedures and practices are also witnessed [6]. Further, mankind, who emphasized in the building construction industry, suffers from accidents and it has affected to the children of construction employees not only the construction workers. These accidents add the pessimistic impacts for the industry and it will result to the labour shortage. This, in turn, upliftment of the safety management and mitigating accidents should be inclined with the involvement of the measurements and assessment [7].

Generally, more than 60,000 fatal accidents have occurred per year around world-wide in the construction sector [8]. The realizable rationalization for the health and safety in building construction industry is cost of hazardous as higher level of fatalities and accidents rather to other industries. Further, in Sri Lankan building construction industry, tremendous number of unskilled and unqualified workers are continuing the engaging with subjected field and consequently, jobsite accidents have been occurred at an unacceptable level. Moreover, insufficient safety awareness, lacking of communication and poor inspection of construction activities are some of the determinations toward the acceleration of the construction [6]. Certain techniques can be made use to mitigate the employee safety like, safety management and safety organizations; safety training; safety policies; safety committees; proper layout and lighting system can be identified [6].

Furthermore, the contractor and the client are the accountable to verify and providing sufficient personal protective equipment and welfare facilities to cater to the workers and increase employee performance [7].

Improving Employee Job Performance has been a notable domain considerably with developing countries. The factors lead to work place hazards due to poor employee health and safety practices which reduce the employee performance, product quality and upgrade the construction cost. Lower rate of health and safety precautionary preventives will lead to demotivation of employees. It directly influences the Employee Job Performance. Employee Job Performance is illustrated as the total expected value to the organization of the separate characteristics that an individual carries out over a standard period of time [9].

Organizational performance is relied up on the Employee Commitment towards the successfully completion of allocated tasks [10]. Committed workers are flourishing man kinds for jobsites in order to step up to the organizational goals. Owing to that consideration, Employee Commitment is elaborated as a competitive advantage for the enterprises [11]. Therefore, superlative Employee Commitment optimistically impact the Employee Job Performance.

Employee job performance is the key factor in the success of the completion of the building construction project. In previous decades, notably, workplace accidents have been increasing at a rapid rate due to various reasons such as un-systematized practices of communication and information network in the workplace; inferior safety procedures and risk management system; lack of jobsite support for health and safety; lack of first-aid support and training; lack of safety and health rules [12]. According to the study of Kaynak et al. in 2016, it has depicted, above subject health and safety practices have an impact on employee job performance. At the same time, Employee

Commitment also influences an Employee Job Performance.

In Sri Lanka, the fatality of the construction industry will lead to a higher number of fatal injuries and deaths. The circulation which has circulated by the Labour Department of Sri Lanka, April 2019, has reported to the industry-related fatalities and accidents against to the years, and in 2011, the construction industry has been 27% of fatal accidents rate against the national index. There are certain researches ([8]; [13]) have been conducted to identify the reasons for accidents in construction sites, the legal aspect of Health and Safety Practices in the construction industry, workers attitudes towards the site safety, and so on, but, it is difficult to find researches under this subject which is the amalgamating of impact on health and safety practices for the Employee Job Performance with effecting of Employee Commitment in the building construction industry. To fill the prevailing gap, the research problem has addressed under this study is as, Do health and safety practices impact on employee job performance with the mediating role of employee commitment in the selected building construction companies in Sri Lanka?

The objectives have been identified for this paper as, To examine how health and safety practices impact on Employee Job Performance in the selected building construction companies in Sri Lanka; To investigate how health and safety practices impact on employee commitment in the selected building construction companies in Sri Lanka; To analyse how employee commitment impact on job performance in the selected building construction companies in Sri Lanka; To explore the mediating role of employee commitment between health and safety practices and employee job performance in the selected building construction companies in Sri Lanka.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Health and Safety Practices and Employee Job Performance

According to the [14] there is an antipathetic impact for employee job performance with inadequate health and safety management practices, insufficient training in safety knowledge, lack of knowledge regarding lethal chemicals and mortal materials, poor monitoring and enforcement of safety rules, insufficient safety equipment. According to the findings of [15] there is an inverse correlation with employee job performance and reducing number of accidents and injuries due to health and safety promotions. Report of the Australian National Commission for Health and Safety (2002), safe working environment in terms of effective Health and safety practices at work place decrease the absenteeism of employees and employee turnover [16] and increase the Employee Performance. It has direct impact on productivity increasing, increasing the employee-employer relationship and eventually, it would lead to higher performance of the organization [17]. Accordingly, the first hypothesis is developed as, Hypothesis 1 (H_1): Health and safety practices has an impact on employee job performance

2.2 Health and Safety Practices and Employee Commitment

According to the findings of Umugwaneza et al in 2019, Health and safety practices at occupational places have notably impacted for Employee commitment and performance with assessing the impact of occupational Health and safety practices Health and safety practices on employee commitment and performance in steel manufacturing company, Rwanda [18]. O'Toole, in 2001, elaborated that Health and safety practices with perception towards the working premises have been positively impacted [19]. Hence the second hypothesis is developed as, Hypothesis 2 (H_2): Health and safety practices has an impact on employee commitment

2.3 Employee Job Performance and Employee Commitment

According to the finding of Fink in 1992, Employee commitment resulted in upgrade the employee job performance [20]. Sutanto in 1999, has illustrated that there is a significant impact of Employee commitment on employee job performance [21]. Furthermore, commitment level of employee leads to employee higher performance level, according to the [22] who conducted a research at Kansai paints. Pakistan researchers have investigated the relationship between employee commitment and their job performances. In relation with their findings, there is a moderate impact on Employee commitment to employee job performance [10]. Accordingly, third hypothesis is developed as: Hypothesis 3 (H_3): Employee commitment has an impact on employee job performance.

2.4 Employee commitment mediates the relationship between health and safety practices and employee job performance

Health and safety practices at occupational premises have a positive and significant impact on employee job performance with mediating effect of Employee commitment [23]. Based on the finding of Liu et al., in 2019, Employee commitment significantly mediates the correlation of Health and safety practices at work places and employee job performance [24]. Hence, final hypothesis is developed as:

Hypothesis 4 (H_4): Employee commitment mediates the relationship between health and safety practices and employee job performance

3. METHOD

Summarizing the research design of this study embedded with study type as analytical, investigation type as causal, researcher interference

as minimal interference, study setting as non-contriving, unit of study as individual, and time horizon as cross sectional. Population as 320, sampling as 175 according to the Krejcie & Morgan table towards the convenience sampling and sample frame is pay roll register. Further, primary data collection method as questionnaire, secondary data collecting as empirical studies. Questionnaires were translated in to Sinhala language and circulated through manual distribution method among the 158 skilled labourers. The descriptive analysis was used to examine the demographic factors of answerers. The data analysis was conducted through IBM-SPSS 23 version analytical software package to examine the hypotheses through regression analysis and correlation analysis. Sobel test was used to measure the mediator effect of the study.

3.1 Measures

In the first section of the questionnaire, referring the findings of several research articles ([12]; [13]; [23]), mainly five components are taken in to this study as components of Health and safety practices at work places comprising, safety procedures and risk management: occupational hazards prevention; organizational safety supports; first aid supports and training; safety and health rules by indicating all 29 well developed questions have been taken into the account from other scholarly work regarding Health and safety practices by Kaynak et al., in 2016 to gather the required information.

In the Second section, referring the previous findings of several research articles ([13]; [22]; [25]; [26]), mainly four dimensions are taken into this study dimension of employee job performance which are, task performance; contextual performance; adaptive performance; counterproductive work behavior by indicating 45 pre-formulated questions that have been taken into the account from study of Koopman's regarding employee job performance. Third section focused in [27] identifications of component of Employee commitment which are,

affective commitment; continuance commitment; normative commitment and 9 well developed questions have been taken into the account from other scholarly work regarding Employee commitment by [22].

Demographic profile is tested by evaluation of the respondents with illustrating three questions as occupational category, age and working experiences.

Respondents were requested to mention their best possible consideration or perception for the given questions through the 5–point Likert scale for first to third parts.

4. RESULTS

Pilot survey was carried out among the 30 respondents from the sample. As per the received questionnaire 152 with indicating 87% of responsive rate, no missing data and no outliers have been identified under the data screening and four multivariate assumptions which are normality, linearity, homoscedasticity and multicollinearity were tested. Table 1 illustrates the normality by assessing the skewness and kurtosis values. Skew standard value of normal distribution is zero (0.000) in terms of it deviates in between -1 to +1. However, [28] have illustrated that the skew value up to +/- 2 is considered as normal distribution. Hence, skew value is less than 2 is the normality distribution range and acceptable kurtosis value is considered less than 4 [28].

Table 1: Assessment of the Normality by Skewness and Kurtosis

		Employee Job Performance	Health and Safety Practices	Employee Commitment
N	Valid	152	152	152
	Missing	0	0	0
Skewness		-0.535	-1.032	0.534
Kurtosis		1.720	1.732	0.389

Skewness and kurtosis value of this study is depicted in Table 1 and it seems that the data set has distributed as normally distribution. The skewness value of health and safety is -1.032, employee job performance is -.535 and the employee commitment is 0.534. Further, kurtosis values for Health and Safety Practices, employee job performance and Employee Commitment as 1.732, 1.720 and 0.389 respectively. This, in turn, it can be recapitulated that, it does not generate the problems related with deviation of normality of particular data set.

Further, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test and Bartlett’s tests were conducted to check the sample adequacy of the data set and above 0.5 values and below 0.05 values respectively ensured the sample adequacy of this data set [29].

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett’s Test Results

Constructs	No of Questions	KMO Values	Bartlett’s test value
HSP	29	0.739	0.000
EJP	45	0.529	0.000
EC	9	0.518	0.000

According to the Table 2, KMO values are indicated as above 0.5 which is exceeded the minimum acceptable level and owing to that, the sample adequacy of this study has been at the appropriate level. Bartlett’s values of three variables have not exceeded the 0.05 which is indicating the significant of the variables in this study.

After that, factor analysis was conducted to examine the most appropriate items for the particular dimensions, and above 0.5 factor loadings ensured the counterpart of the data set [30]. As per the immense of factor loading values in this study exceed the required level which is the minimum of 0.5 except three items of the Employee Job Performance. Those three items are deleted for further analysis.

As per the Table 3 which the Cronbach’s alpha values have been exceeded 0.700 which is at the acceptable level and, in a consequence, the reliability of the study constructs is ensured [29].

Table 3: Reliability Assessment Results

Constructs	Items		Cronbach’s Alpha	
Health and Safety Practices		29		0.901
Safety procedures and risk management	06		0.802	
Occupational hazards prevention	07		0.753	
Organizational Safety Supports	05		0.777	
First-aid supports and trainings	04		0.826	
Safety and health rules	07		0.706	
Employee Job Performance		42		0.842
Task Performance	10		0.931	
Adaptive Performance	08		0.779	
Contextual Performance	15		0.844	
Counterproductive Work Behavior	09		0.769	
Employee Commitment		09		0.869
Affective Commitment	03		0.716	
Continuance Commitment	03		0.901	
Normative Commitment	03		0.911	

Construct validity was ensured owing to the constructing of hypotheses with the quality literature and conceptualized and operationalized also based on the literature. Further, Convergent validity and discriminant validity were tested with Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values and Composite Reliability (CR) values. AVE with above 0.5 ensured the convergent validity of the constructs.

Table 4: Assessment of the Convergent Validity

Construct	No of Items	Convergent Validity		
		Factor Loading > 0.5 Min - Max	CR > 0.7	AVE > 0.5
HSP	29	0.500 – 0.979	0.983	0.733
EJP	42	0.562 – 0.974	0.985	0.730
EC	09	0.627 – 0.977	0.964	0.789

Table 4 demonstrates the CR and AVE values are exceeded as 0.700 which ensures the convergent validity in this study.

4.1 Demographic Profile Analysis

Occupation categories categorized under three categories namely, mason, carpenter, and riggers which is under skilled labor categorization, and it is highlighted that the majority of 44% of respondents are masons and the 31% of respondents are riggers whereas 25% of respondents are carpenters. Five groups were recognized to gather the information regarding age of respondents in terms of skilled labourers ages namely, 21–25; 26–30; 31–35; 35–40 and above 40, and it is highlighted that the majority of 48% of respondents are in age between 36 to 40 years. The second majority of employees are in age between 26 to 30 years and it is 19 percent. Further, 17% of employees age over 40 years and 7% of employees’ age between 21 to 25 years. Working experience of the respondents are divided into six ranges comprising, below 3 months; 3–6 months; 6 months –1 year; 1–2 years; 2–3 years and above 3 years, and it is indicated that the majority of 55% of employees have working experience over three years of time and 14% of employees have two to three years of working experience. Further, 12% of employees have experienced of 3 to 6 month and 10% of employees have below 3 months of working experience.

4.2 Testing Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1 (H₁)

Regression analysis is conducted for examining the impact of independent variable (Health and safety practices) on dependent variable (Employee Job Performance).

Table 5: Model Summary H₁

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Constant	B value	Std. Error of the estimate	Sig value
1	0.598 ^a	0.358	0.353	2.220	0.340	0.18111	.000 ^b

As per the Table 5, R value which is multiple regression coefficient of the Health and safety practices and Employee Job Performance is 0.598 and R square value is indicated as 0.358. That means, approximately 35.8% of the variance which is R square elaborated by the Health and safety practices. Further, Table 5 depicts the constant value and B value as 2.220 and 0.340 respectively. This, in turn, the regression equation of Employee Job Performance can be demonstrated as, Employee Job Performance = 2.220 + 0.340 (Health and safety practices). Moreover, sig value (p-value) is depicted as 0.000 which is less than the 0.05 significant value and verifying the Health and safety practices which is independent variable can be used to forecast Employee Job Performance which is dependent variable in terms of H₁ is validated.

Hypothesis 2 (H₂)

Regression analysis is conducted for scrutinizing the impact of Health and safety practices on employee commitment.

Table 6: Model Summary for H₂

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Constant	B value	Std. Error of the	Sig value
1	0.231 ^a	0.053	0.047	2.426	0.313	0.52360	.004 ^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Constant	B value	Std. Error of the estimate	Sig value
2	0.754 ^a	0.568	0.565	2.329	0.316	0.14855	.000 ^b

As per the Table 6, R value which is multiple regression coefficient of the Health and safety practices and employee commitment is 0.231 and R square value is indicated as 0.053. That means, approximately 5.3% of the variance which is R square elaborated by the Health and safety practices. The constant value and B value as 2.426 and 0.313 respectively. This, in turn, the regression equation of employee commitment can be demonstrated as, employee commitment = 2.426 + 0.313 (Health and safety practices). Further, sig value (p-value) is depicted as 0.004 which is less than the 0.05 significant value and verifying the Health and safety practices which is independent variable can be used to forecast Employee Commitment which is dependent variable in terms of H₂ is validated.

Hypothesis 3 (H₃)

Regression analysis is conducted for scrutinizing the impact of Employee Job Performance on EC.

Table 7: Model Summary for H₃

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Constant	B value	Std. Error of the estimate	Sig value
3	0.754 ^a	0.568	0.565	2.329	0.316	0.14855	.000 ^b

As per the Table 7, R value which is multiple regression coefficient of the Employee Job Performance and employee commitment is 0.754 and R square value is indicated as 0.568. That

means, approximately 56.8% of the variance which is R square elaborated by the employee commitment. Further, Table 7 illustrates the constant value and B value as 2.329 and 0.316 respectively. This, in turn, the regression equation of EC can be demonstrated as, Employee Job Performance = 2.329 + 0.316(employee commitment). Moreover, sig value (p-value) is depicted as 0.000 which is less than the 0.05 significant value and verifying the Employee Job Performance which is independent variable can be used to forecast employee commitment which is dependent variable in terms of H₃ is validated.

Hypothesis 4 (H₄)

Sobel test was used to examine the mediating effect of employee commitment on relationship between Health and safety practices and Employee Job Performance. Figure 2 illustrates the Sobel test results of this study.

Figure 2: Sobel Test Results

As per the above calculation, Sobel test statistic indicates as 2.852 and to complete the mediating effect, the 2-tailed p value should be less than the 0.05 [31] and this study indicates as 0.004 with fulfilled the mediating effect. Figure 3 elaborates the direct and indirect effect to Employee Job Performance.

Figure 3: Assessment of Mediating Effect

5. DISCUSSION

Regression analysis results ($\beta = 0.340$, $t\text{-value} = 2.220$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000$) witnessing the positive amalgamation between Health and safety practices and Employee Job Performance in terms of Health and safety practices has a positive impact over Employee Job Performance.

As per the literatures, there are considerable number of empirical studies that have scrutinized impact and consistent of Health and safety practices on Employee Job Performance, and it has illustrated the positive impact by [13]; [14]; [15]; [17]; [18]; [32]; [33]; [34]; [35]; [36] and further, Report of the Australian National Commission for Health and Safety in 2002 has implied the impact on Employee Job Performance of Health and safety practices. Further, the social cognitive theory, safety climate theory and Domino theory have rationale illustrated that the Health and safety practices uplift the Employee Job Performance by assisting health and safety education towards the hazardous free jobsite in order to increase the skills and performance for achieving tasks safely in terms of First-aid Supports

and Training and Organizational Safety Support; increasing of employee job performance with effect of shared perception comprising health and safety policies, procedures and practices specially towards the employee psychological well-being in terms of Safety Procedures and Risk Managements and Safety and Health Rules; protecting from the hazardous situations in terms of Occupational Hazards Prevention respectively.

Current study tested the impact of Health and safety practices on Employee Job Performance by skilled labourers who are engaged with building construction activities which is essential of the health and safety practices (Mason, Carpenters and Riggers) in selected building construction companies in Sri Lanka. Hence, the study findings revealed the impact of Health and safety practices on Employee Job Performance and it indicated the positive impact and consistent of Health and safety practices on Employee Job Performance in terms of enhancement of the Health and safety practices is led to upgrade of Employee Job Performance in building construction industry in Sri Lanka.

The regression analysis results ($\beta = 0.313$, t -value=2.426, p -value= 0.004) with witnessing the positive relationship between Health and safety practices and EC in terms of Health and safety practices has a positive impact on employee commitment.

According to the previous studies, considerable numbers of studies have been undertaken to recognize the impact and consistent of Health and safety practices on employee commitment comprising, [18]; [19]; [37]; [38]; [39];[40] . Aforementioned literatures, have illustrated the impact of Health and safety practices on employee commitment.

Amponsah-Tawiah & Mensah depicted that the moderate positive impact and consistent of Health and safety practices on EC, and certain reasons have been elaborated for it [39]. It is built up reciprocation in employees' mind regarding the cost

effectiveness for the enhancement of health and safety practices namely, investments for employee's health and safety, cost for safety training and ect would be impacted to their payments, and until the payments have been completed, it is unable to take out the expected performances of employees for given tasks [41]. Further, Sinclai, et al., illustrated that, when the increasement of health and safety at the jobsites, employees misunderstand that, their health and safety is under peril and it can likely to rise the absenteeism, high turnover and etc. and it causes to lessen the employee's expected commitment for their duties [40].

As per the social exchange theory, people evaluate the potential upwards and downwards related to the relationships. There is a tendency towards the termination and abundant the relationship, when the demerits are more outweighed to merits. Hence, the fundamental desirability of secure life at workplaces, employees will incline to evaluate the relationship with the jobsite by increasing their commitment toward the assigned duties [42].

This, in turn, the findings of this study also enumerates as the emperical study under the Sri Lankan building construction industry by validating the positive impact of Health and safety practices on employee commitment with witnessing the consistent of this hypothesis.

The regression analysis results ($\beta = 0.316$, t -value=2.329, p -value= 0.000) with witnessing the positive relationship between Employee Job Performance and employee commitment in terms of employee commitment has a positive impact on Employee Job Performance.

Considerable numbers of studies have been conducted to recognize the impact on Employee Job Performance of employee commitment and it is consistent with previous studies such as, [10]; [11]; [20]; [22]; [43]; [44]. Aforementioned literatures have demonstrated positive impact on Employee Job Performance of employee commitment. Adnan et al. have illustrated that the positive impact on

Employee Job Performance of employee commitment with studying the employees of Kansai paint in Pakistan [22]. Hence, the findings of this study also adds as the empirical study under the Sri Lankan building construction industry by validating the positive impact on Employee Job Performance of employee commitment

The final hypothesis is aimed to response for fourth objective.

Sobel test results were used to elaborate the above-mentioned mediating effect to the relationship of Health and safety practices and Employee Job Performance. As per the data set, Sobel test statistic indicated as 2.852 and the 2-tailed p value indicated as 0.004 with witnessing the mediating effect of employee commitment for relationship between Health and safety practices and Employee Job Performance.

According to the literatures, certain number of studies have examined the mediating effect of employee commitment for relationship between Health and safety practices and Employee Job Performance comprising, [23] and [24]. However, immense number of empirical studies have been conducted employee commitment as the mediating variable, but it is not exactly amalgamated with Health and safety practices and Employee Job Performance.

This, in turn, the findings of this study also enumerates as the empirical study under the Sri Lankan building construction industry by validating the positive, significant mediating effect of employee commitment for relationship between Health and safety practices and employee commitment.

6. CONCLUSION

Fundamental identification of this study sums up with the dynamic, emerging and challenging domain of human resource management in this contemporary era which is denoting as the health and safety practices as, employees' health, safety

and welfare at the working premises. The current study addresses the research problem in this study as, the identification of impact of Health and safety practices on Employee Job Performance with mediating effect of employee commitment among the 152 of skilled labourers (mason, carpenters and riggers) in C1 category according to the Institute of Construction Training and Development (ICTAD) registration of selected building construction companies in Sri Lanka.

The finding of the study was aligned with both direct and indirect impact of Health and safety practices on Employee Job Performance and further tested another two hypotheses as impact of Health and safety practices on employee commitment, impact on Employee Job Performance of employee commitment for garnering the confirmation of this study. However, by analyzing the collected data under questionnaire survey, established four hypotheses implied the positive significant impact with accepting all four hypotheses in this study.

Study output revealed the employer should pay attention for the enhancement of the employees' health and safety at the building construction site as construction industry is one of the most hazardous industries in the world. Imposing of safety and health policies, strategies and procedures should be implemented by the relevant personalities towards the better prospect of the employees and the building construction firm is another practical implication. Furnishing the required first-aid stuff and trainings the workers about the first-aid methods has added to the practical implication category. Making a convenient, risk-free working environment for the employee is also weighed with the practical implications. Moreover, for achieving the ultimate objective of the building construction industry, Employee Job Performance is the upmost requirement, and with these positive relationships as per the study results of Health and safety practices at workplaces lead to upgrade the Employee Job Performance. Finally, that is resulted to accomplish

the objectives towards the sustainability development of the Sri Lankan building construction industry.

REFERENCES

- [1] Durdyev, S., & Ismail, S. (2012). Role of the construction industry in economic development of Turkmenistan. *Energy Science and Research* 2012, 883–890.
- [2] Khan, R. A. (2005). Role of Construction Sector in Economic Growth: Empirical Evidence from Pakistan Economy. *Advancing and Integrating Construction Education*, 1–13.
- [3] Dlamini, S. (2012). Relationship of construction sector to economic growth. *School of Construction Management and Engineering*, 1–12.
- [4] Tiwary, G., Gangopadhyay, P. K., Biswas, S., Nayak, K., Chatterjee, M. K., Chakraborty, D., & Mukherjee, S. (2012). Socio-economic status of workers of building construction industry. *Indian journal of occupational and environmental medicine*, 16(2), 66.
- [5] Editorial team. (2017). *Construction Tuts*. Retrieved January 29, 2021, from <https://www.constructiontuts.com/construction-industry/>
- [6] Kanchana, S., Sivaprakash, P., & Josep, S. (2015). Studies on Labour Safety in Construction Sites. *Thee Scientific World Journal*, 1–7.
- [7] Darshana, D. W. (2017). Improvement of Health and Safety in Construction Sites in Sri Lanka. *Engineer vol 1*, 53–70.
- [8] Jazayeri, E., & Dadi, G. B. (2017). Construction Safety Management Systems and Methods of Safety Performance Measurement: A Review. *Journal of Safety Engineering*, 15–28.
- [9] Motowidlo, S. J., & Kell, H. J. (2012). Job Performance. *Industrial and organizational psychology*, 91–130.
- [10] Dost, M. K., & Tariq, S. (2012). Employee Commitment and Their Performance are Inter-Related: A behavioral Study from Pakistan. *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 125–139.
- [11] Sutanto, E. M. (1999). The Relationship Between Employee Commitment and Job Performance. *Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship*, 47–55.
- [12] Kaynak, R., Toklu, A., Meral, E., & Toklu, I. T. (2016). Effects of Occupational Health and Safety Practices on Organizational Commitment, Work Alienation, and Job Performance: Using the PLS-SEM Approach. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 1–22.
- [13] Perera, G. (2019). Occupational Health and Safety Practice and Job Performance: Role of Job Satisfaction. *Sri Lankan Journal of Human Resource Management*, 9(1), 1–10.
- [14] Agbola, R. M. (2012). Impact of Health and Safety Management on Employee Safety at the Ghana Ports and Harbour Authority. *International Knowledge sharing platform*, 2(9), pp. 156–166.
- [15] Dwomoh, G., Owusu, E. E., & Addo, M. (2013). Impact of occupational health and safety policies on employees' performance in the Ghana's timber industry: Evidence from Lumber and Logs Limited. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 1(12). Retrieved from <http://ijern.com/journal/December-2013/38.pdf>
- [16] NOSH. (2002). Australian National Occupational Health and Safety Commission, Annual Report 2002–03. Canberra: National Occupational Health and Safety Commission.
- [17] U, I. M., & Tom, E. E. (2016). Effects of Industrial Safety and Health on Employees' Job Performance in Selected Cement Companies in Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Review*, 49–56.
- [18] Umugwaneza, C., Nkechi, I. E., & Mugabe, J. B. (2019). Effect of Workplace Safety and Health Practices on Employee Commitment and Performance in Steel Manufacturing Companies in Rwanda. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 1–11.
- [19] O'Toole, M. (2001). The relationship between employees' perceptions of safety and organizational culture. *Journal of Safety Research*, p. 231–243.
- [20] Fink, S. L. (1992). *High commitment workplaces*. New York: Quorum Books.
- [21] Sutanto, E. M. (1999). The Relationship Between Employee Commitment and Job Performance. *Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship*, 47–55.
- [22] Adnan, Sonia; Nhaily, Abir; Wang, Hongyu. (2018). To Evaluate and Study the relationship between employees' commitment and individual performance, s.l.: s.n
- [23] Mulyantoro, H., Haryono, S. & Fauziyah. (2018). Analysis of influence of Occupational Safety and Health and job satisfaction to employee performance with commitment organizational intervening variable. *International Journal of Business Quantitative and Economics and Applied Management Research*, 5(3)
- [24] Liu, S. et al., 2019. Occupational Health and Safety and Turnover Intention in the Ghanaian Power Industry: The Mediating Effect of Organizational Commitment. *BioMed Research International*.
- [25] Viswesvaran, C., & Ones, D. S. (2000). Perspectives on Models of Job Performance. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 216–226.

- [26] Koopmans, L. et al., 2014. Measuring Individual Work Performance—Identifying and Selecting Indicators. *A Journal of Prevention, Assessment & Rehabilitation*, 16 May, Volume 3, pp. 62–81
- [27] Allen, N. J., & Meyer, J. P. (1990). The measurement and antecedents affective, continuance and normative commitment to the organization. *Journal of Occupational Psychology*(1990), 1–18
- [28] West, S. G., Finch, J. F. & Curran, P. J., 1996. Structural equation models with nonnormal variables: problems and remedies.. pp. 56–75
- [29] Glen, S.(2014). 'Univariate Analysis', *Statistic how To.com*, viewed at 9 December 2020, <<https://www.statisticshowto.com/univariate/>>.
- [30] Sekaran, U (2003). *Research Methods for Business*, Edn. 4, John Wiley & Sons, New York.
- [31] Bontis, N., Booker, L. D. & Serenko, A., 2007. The mediating effect of organizational reputation on customer loyalty and service recommendation in the banking industry. 45(9), pp. 1426–1445.
- [32] Yusuf, R. M., Eliyana, A., & Sari, O. N. (2012). The Influence of Occupational Safety and Health on Performance with Job Satisfaction as Intervening Variables (Study on the Production Employees in PT. Mahakarya Rotanindo, Gresik). *American Journal of Economics*, 136–1 40. doi:10.5923/j.economics.20120001.30
- [33] Felix, B. O. (2012). Effects of Organizational Health and Safety Policies on Employees' Performance in Larfarge (WAPCO) Plc. Ewekoro, Ogun State. 1–87.
- [34] Goetzel, R. (1999). *Health and Productivity Management II, measuring and reporting workforce productivity, best practice*. Houston.
- [35] Sgroi, D. (2015). *Happiness and productivity: Understanding the happy-productive worker*. SMF-CAGE Global Perspectives Series.
- [36] Rathnaweera, R. R., & Fernando, A. P. (2019). Impact of Human Resource Management Practices on Machine Operators' Performance: With Special Reference to the Apparel Factories in Kalutara District, Sri Lanka. 4th Interdisciplinary Conference of Management Researchers Sabaragamuwa University of Sri Lanka.
- [37] Amponsah-Tawiah, K., & Mensah, J. (2016). Occupational Health and Safety and Organizational Commitment: Evidence from the Ghanaian Mining Industry. *Journal of Safety and Health at work*, 7(3), 225–230.
- [38] Renata. (2020, May). ohsrep. Retrieved from https://www.ohsrep.org.au/duties_of_employees
- [39] Sinclair, R. R., Tucker, J. S., & Cullen, J. C. (2005). Performance Differences Among Four Organizational Commitment Profiles. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 90(6), 1280–1287. doi:0.1037/0021-9010.90.6.1280
- [40] Zeidan, S. (2006). Workers' Affective Commitment and their Willingness to Perform Discretionary Work Behaviour: the Impact of Commitment-Oriented Human Resources Management Practices. *Journal of Business Systems, Governance and Ethics*, 1(1). Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/ab0a/43891c2dc81eb318bf4536e9bb49605a3bc1.pdf>
- [41] Gruen, T. W., Summers, J. O., & Acito, F. (2000). Relationship Marketing Activities, Commitment, and Membership Behaviors in Professional Associations. *Journal of Marketing*, 64(3), 34–49.
- [42] Cook, K. S., & Rice, E. (2006). Social Exchange Theory. *Social Forces*, 53–56.
- [43] Mathieu, J. E. & Zajac, D. (1990). A Review and Meta-Analysis of the Antecedents, Correlates, and Consequences of Organizational Commitment. *Scientific Journal*, pp. 171–194.
- [44] Mowday, R., Porter, L. & Steers, R., 1982. *Employee–Organization Linkages: The Psychology of Commitment, Absenteeism, and Turnover*